

32- and 28-Macrocyclic polyammonium cations assisted pseudo two-dimensional assembly of citrate stabilized gold nanoparticles

Tarun Kumar Misra*^a, Diptanu Debnath^a and Tse-Hsien Chen^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Agartala-799 055, Tripura, India

E-mail : t_k_misra@yahoo.com

^bEYES Testing Laboratory, Yung Shin Pharma. Ind. Co. Ltd., Taichung, Taiwan

Manuscript received online 16 July 2013, revised 26 September 2013, accepted 01 November 2014

Abstract : Macrocyclic polyammonium cations (MCPAC), [32]ane-(NH₂⁺)₈.8Cl⁻ (32-MCPAC), and [28]ane-(NH₂⁺)₆O₂.6Cl⁻ (28-MCPAC), which are highly water soluble, are well reputed for their anion recognition and metal nanoparticles (MNPs) stabilization properties. First time, we have employed them as cross-linkers for organizing negatively charged citrate-stabilized gold nanoparticles (Au-NPs) into a pseudo two-dimensional (2-D) array. Assembled Au-NPs were characterized by UV-Vis spectroscopy and Transmission Electronic Microscopy (TEM). The UV-Vis spectrum of citrate-stabilized Au-NPs so prepared of diameter ~12 nm shows Surface Plasmon Resonance (SRP) at *ca.* 520 nm, indicating discrete nature of Au-NPs. The UV-Vis spectra of Au-NPs in the presence of 32-/28-MCPAC show red-shifted and broadened SRP maxima centered at *ca.* 580 nm for 32-MCPAC and at *ca.* 605 nm for 28-MCPAC which are attributed to the inter-particle plasmon absorbance, indicating large compact isotropic assembly of Au-NPs. The concrete evidence was obtained from the TEM images which reveal that the particles are arranged pseudo 2-D without any severe agglomeration. Photographs of all the solutions were taken and indicate how the color of almost discrete Au-NPs (wine-red color) changes to get assembled Au-NPs (bluish). The study of pH effect on assembling Au-NPs reveals that the electrostatic attraction followed by hydrogen bonding interaction between MCPAC and citrate ions leads to the formation of 2-D array of Au-NPs. In addition, at pH 12.30 when the cross-linking property of MCPACs was nullified, Au-NPs were formed rod-like aggregation. Assembled Au-NPs would be futuristic promising materials, especially for optoelectronic devices.

Keywords : Gold nanoparticles, macrocyclic polyammonim cations, assembly, 2-D array, water.

Introduction

Gold nanoparticles (Au-NPs) are the most stable metal nanoparticles (MNPs) and exhibit fascinating aspects such as multi-dimensional assembly in material science, individualistic behavior of particles, size related electronic, magnetic and optical properties and their applications to catalysis and biology¹⁻³. Moreover, self-assembly MNPs are of extremely important because of their potential applications in biosensors⁴⁻⁶, optics⁷, catalysis⁸, electronics⁹, surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS)^{10,11}, surface plasmon spectroscopy (SPS)¹² and so on. Thus, research efforts toward the organizing nanoparticles (zero dimensional, 0-D) into one- (1-D), two- (2-D), and three- (3-D) dimensional arrays have therefore been rapidly expanding in recent years¹³⁻²². Among several approaches, the organization of MNPs into 1-D or 2-D arrays offers a promising strategy to tailor the flux of surface plasmons²³.

The approach of fabricating chainlike 1-D MNPs arrays has been reported by following the templates or ligand exchange processes. Similarly, fabrication of 2-D arrays of metallic nanoparticles can be performed in the presence of template or coupling agents such as surfactants, inorganic crystals or proteins. However, the stable assembly of nanoparticles in water along with other solids is extremely important for the study of SERS or SPS. Sastry *et al.*²⁴ and Mayya *et al.*²⁵ reported in controlling aggregation process of carboxylate-functionalized nanoparticles in water by regulating pH of the solutions. Shipway *et al.*¹⁹ investigated electrostatically induced aggregation of citrate-stabilized gold nanoparticles in the presence of cationic molecules or cationic nanoparticles. In addition, Orbach *et al.*¹⁴ and Beverina²⁶ monitored the assembly of gold nanoparticles using organic especially pyridine-based cross-linkers. Here, we report a study

of formation of pseudo 2-D assembly of citrate-stabilized gold nanoparticles in water using macrocyclic polyammonium cations (MCPAC). The use of MCPAC for this novel purpose is a unique endeavor.

Macrocyclic polyammonium cations are cyclic protonated secondary aliphatic polyamines. They are highly water soluble and well known receptors for anions or anionic species because of the high cationic charge on its protonated form. Protonation introduces rigidity into the receptor because positive charges on adjacent nitrogen's tend to adopt anti-conformations to minimize electrostatic repulsion, resulting in a more circular shape²⁷. The [32]ane-(NH₂⁺)₈.8Cl⁻ (32-MCPAC) and [28]ane-(NH₂⁺)₆O₂.6Cl⁻ (28-MCPAC) were chosen as macrocyclic polyammonium cations and their chemical structures are depicted in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Chemical structures of 32-/28-MCPAC.

Synthesis and anion recognition properties of these molecules are well-documented²⁷⁻³⁰. The chemical structure of 32-MCPAC and 28-MCPAC, exhibit eight and six protonated secondary aliphatic amines in their cyclic forms with equal number of chloride ions as counter anions, respectively. We reported earlier the synthesis of underivatized Au- and Ag-NPs in the presence of 32- and 28-MCPAC³¹⁻³⁴. It has been illustrated that they are not only stabilized the MNPs effectively but also functionalized them for sensing anions or nucleotides. Bioconjugation of as-synthesized Au-NPs with Bovine Serum Albumine (BSA) has also been studied. In the present investigation, we explore another extremely important novel property of macrocyclic polyammonium cations for their exploitation in assembling of citrate stabilized Au-NPs in water and report herein. As they are carrying multiple positive charges, it is relevant for choosing them for this novel

purpose as the citrate stabilized Au-NPs are having negative surface charges. MCPACs being circular shape and carrying multiple charges can act as cross-linkers for drawing scattered negatively charged Au-NPs electrostatically very close to make into 2-D arrays.

Results and discussion

Ultraviolet-visible spectral analysis :

Surface plasmon resonance (SRP) of Au-NPs is a good diagnostic tool for the formation of the nanoparticles as well as its nature of association. A UV-Vis spectrum and a TEM micrograph of citrated-stabilized Au-NPs so prepared were taken and are shown in Fig. 1. The spectrum (Fig. 1A) shows an absorption band centered at 520 nm. The TEM image in Fig. 1B reveals that the average particle size is around 12 nm.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the UV-Vis spectra of citrate stabilized Au-NPs in the presence of 32- and 28-MCPAC, respectively. Several aqueous solutions with different molar ratios of Au-NPs to MCPAC were studied and recorded their corresponding UV-Vis spectra in different time interval. Fig. 2(A-D) represents the UV-Vis spectra of citrate stabilized Au-NPs in the presence of 32-MCPAC of molar ratios Au-NPs : 32-MCPAC as 1 : 3 (A), 1 : 2 (B), 2 : 3 (C) and 1 : 1 (D), respectively. From the molar ratio it is clear that the molar concentration of Au-NPs was kept increasing from 'A' to 'D' solutions. In Fig. 2A, it is seen that the intensity of the SRP band maximum ($\lambda = 525$ nm, 0 h) of Au-NPs spectrum decreases noticeably and the spectrum becomes broadened (at the center of the band, $\lambda = 580$ nm, 4 h) with a time interval of 4 h. The spectrum becomes broadened (at the center of the band, $\lambda = 580$ nm), almost immediately and gets little bit

Fig. 1. Citrate stabilized Au-NPs. (A) UV-Vis spectrum and (B) TEM image.

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of Au-NPs with 32-MCPAC in various molar ratios. Molar ratios of Au-NPs : 32-MCPAC (A) 1 : 3, (B) 1 : 2, (C) 2 : 3, (D) 1 : 1; period after spectra recorded : (a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 2 h, (d) 3 h, (e) 4 h.

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra of Au-NPs with 28-MCPAC in various molar ratios. Molar ratios of Au-NPs : 28-MCPAC (A) 1 : 3, (B) 2 : 3, period after spectra recorded : (a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 12 h, (d) 13 h.

less intensive with time when the molar ratio was made 1 : 2 (Fig. 2B). When the proportion of Au-NPs in the solutions increases further in case of Fig. 2C or 2D, neither the exterior feature of the spectrum which is identical of Fig. 2B, nor the intensity of the curve changes with time.

Citrate stabilized Au-NPs are indeed stable and exhibit the UV-Vis spectrum with maximum absorbance of SRP band at 520 nm as shown in Fig. 1A. The UV-Vis spectral bands of citrate stabilized Au-NPs in the presence MCPAC are also resulted from the surface plasmon resonance of the Au-NPs. The SRP band of well dispersed Au-NPs is calculated theoretically to be at 510–525 nm in an aqueous solution³⁵. It is evident that for spherical metal nanoparticles of size 3–20 nm, the absorption spectrum is fully independent on particle size³⁵. This is because for particle sizes below *ca.* 20 nm in diameter, the quadruple and higher-order terms in the Mie summation become significant³⁶. The source of surface plasmon resonance in this region is due to the transverse oscillation of the surface electrons. It has been reported that the red-shifting and broadening of the transverse band along with the appearance of a long wavelength band which is termed as the longitudinal band origi-

nated from the longitudinal oscillation of electrons, is observed when individual particles are aligned into a definite array or agglomerate^{37,38}. The SRP band at *ca.* 520 nm of Au-NPs in UV-Vis spectrum (Fig. 1A) can be treated as transverse band which is the characteristic of discrete Au-NPs. Whereas, the red-shifted and broadened band at *ca.* 580 nm of Au-NPs in the presence of 32-MCPAC which having multiple charges acting cross-linkers, can be treated as a longitudinal band (i.e. interparticle plasmon coupling band) for the definite dimensional array or assembly or in agglomerated state of Au-NPs. Mann *et al.*³⁷ reported such type of spectral change for the change of SRP bands of citrated stabilized Au-NPs in the presence of mercaptoethyl alcohol (MEA) experimentally and studied simulation theoretically. They demonstrated that the broad band at about 580–600 nm was due to the presence of large compact isotropic aggregates. Shipway *et al.*¹⁹ established that multiple charged cross-linkers could bind NPs together into dense, multiple layered aggregates and showed absorbance band above 650 nm. In our case, the interparticle plasmon band appeared to at *ca.* 580 nm can thus be indicative of heavy compact isotropic aggregation.

Fig. 2A to 2D reveals that with the increase of molar concentration of Au-NPs the broadening of the SRP band

is being fast. In case of Fig. 2C and 2D there is an immediate effect. The Table shows the shifting of SRP bands with different molar ratios of Au-NPs to 32-MCPAC. The data of the Table 1 indicates that while keeping molar concentration of 32-MCPAC constant the red-shifting of SRP band of Au-NPs occurring from 520 nm for molar ratio 1 : 0 to 610 nm for molar ratio 6 : 1 is due to the increase of concentration of Au-NPs. Further increasing concentration of Au-NPs (molar ratio, 6 : 1 to 200 : 1) the SRP band shifted to 628 nm. Thus, the rate of aggregation increases with the increase of concentration of Au-NPs that expresses the MCPACs optima. A transition from single layer aggregation to multiple layer aggregation is also observed (from the data of the Table 1) when the molar ratio of Au-NPs to 32-MCPACs exceeds to 6 : 1.

Table 1. Absorption maxima of Au-NPs mixed with 32-MCPAC

Au-NPs : 32-MCPAC ^a	Wavelength (nm)
1 : 0	520.4
1 : 1	575.4
2 : 1	580.0
3 : 1	580.0
4 : 1	580.0
5 : 1	580.0
5.5 : 1	595.0
6 : 1	610.0
7 : 1	614.0
8 : 1	628.0
9 : 1	628.0
10 : 1	628.0
100 : 1	628.0
200 : 1	628.0

^aMolar ratio of Au-NPs : 32-MCPAC.

There are two possible mechanisms of formation of Au-NPs array by the MCPAC that seem to act : (i) the pH of the aqueous solution of 32-MCPAC is 4.20 whereas its pKa values ranges from 6.95 to 10.70³². Thus, in its aqueous solution 32-MCPAC remains fully protonated (-NH₂⁺) forms and bears net positive charge. On the other hand, the three pKa values³⁹ of citric acid are 3.13, 4.76 and 6.40 and the pH of the as-prepared citrate-stabilized Au-NPs is 6.50. Thus, it is evident that the citrate ions onto the Au-surface adsorbs as negatively charged ions (producing a ζ potential) and providing stability to

Au-NPs by electrostatic force of repulsion. Moreover, the slowly but noticeably decrease of intensity of SRP maxima of citrate stabilized Au-NPs in Fig. 2A and somewhat in case of Fig. 2B may be attributed to the proton transfer from the 32-MCPAC moiety to citrate ions onto the Au-surface (Scheme 2A). Thereby, the partial transformation of -COO⁻ group in the citrate moiety into acidic forms, -COOH, by combining with H⁺ ions furnished by 32-MCPAC occurs, resulting decrease of negative charges as well as ζ potential of the Au-NPs. As a consequence of decreasing of negative charges on the Au-surface leads to van der Waals force assisted assembly. *In situ* produced H⁺ ions assisted Au-NPs assembly was reported by Xu *et al.*³⁹; (ii) In case of Fig. 2C and 2D, the spectra become broadened almost immediately and the features remain unchanged with time. It may be attributed to the formation of assembly of Au-NPs by the electrostatic force of attraction followed by hydrogen bonding interaction between positively charged 32-MCPAC and negatively charged citrate ions (Scheme 2B). As the overall pH of such solutions of molar ratios become around 6.50, it is presumed that the 32-MCPAC and Au-NPs/citrate-ions could hold their corresponding charges. Being a well-known anion recognizer, it is expected that the 32-MCPAC draws the citrate ions from the Au-surface into its core and make hydrogen bond interaction (-COO⁻...H-NH⁺) within them (Scheme 2B). Two such driving force of interaction slower the ζ potential of the Au-NPs more effectively and make them uncapped, leading the formation of assembly of Au-NPs fast. Thus, unlike van der Waals force assisted assembly in the first case, the electrostatic force of attraction followed by hydrogen bonding interaction between 32-MCPAC and citrate ions brings the Au-NPs at the close proximity to make them assembly. A schematic illustration is portrayed in Scheme 2.

The almost identical but little bit more broadened of UV-Vis spectra of citrated stabilized Au-NPs in the presence 28-MCPAC instead of 32-MCPAC were observed. Two representative UV-Vis spectra of molar ratio of Au-NPs to 28-MCPAC, 1 : 3 (λ = 580 nm, 0 h – 605 nm, 12 h) and 2 : 3 (at the center of the band, λ = 605 nm) are given in Figs. 3A and 3B. The reason of more broadened spectra in this case may be due to the decrease of size of the MCPAC. 28-MCPAC being smaller in size draws the particles more close and consequently increase the inter-

(A) Proton transfer from 32-MCPAC to citrate ion onto the Au-surface

(B) Transfer of citrate ion from the Au-surface into the 32-MCPAC core

Scheme 2. Schematic illustration for the assembly of Au-NPs via (A) proton transfer; (B) citrate ion capitulation.

particle plasmon absorbance. This phenomenon had also been investigated by Shipway *et al.*¹⁹. UV-Vis spectra (Fig. 3) reveal that the stability of discrete Au-NPs decreases with the decrease of molar concentration of 28-MCPAC instead the particles approaches to close vicinity and arrange themselves into an array. Thus, from the above discussion it is proved that when the molar concentration of MCPACs is greater than the molar concentration of citrated-stabilized Au-NPs, the pH of the solution must less than 5.00 and the lowering of ζ potential of the Au-NPs may occur due to the proton transfer from the MCPAC to citrate ions onto the Au-surface. While the molar concentration of MCPACs is less than the molar concentration of citrated-stabilized Au-NPs, the pH of the solution becomes about 6.50 which may initiate electrostatic attraction cum hydrogen bonding capitulation of citrate ions from the Au-surface.

Effect of charges of MCPAC on Au-NPs array :

The pKa values of 32-/28-MCPAC are ranges from 6.95 to 10.70 whereas the pKa values³⁹ of citric acid are 3.13, 4.76 and 6.40. Moreover, aqueous solution of 32-MCPAC and of 28-MCPAC are acidic with pH of 4.20 and 4.55, respectively³². It indicates that they remain fully protonated in their aqueous solution. De-protonation occurs with increase in pH of solutions causing decreasing the net positive charge of the MCPACs. Exploiting this phenomenon the nature of assembly of Au-NPs in the presence of 28-MCPAC at different pH were studied with UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The solutions of

28-MCPAC at pH 6.50, 8.84, 11.50 and 12.30 were mixed with the Au-NPs solution maintaining the molar ratio 2 : 3 (Au-NPs to 28-MCPAC). In order to prevent protonation of citrate moiety onto the surface of Au-NPs and to tune the positive charge of the MCPAC the minimum pH was chosen as >6.40 . The corresponding UV-Vis spectra are shown in Fig. 4(A-D). At pH 6.50 the UV-Vis spectra (at the center of the band, $\lambda = 605$ nm) shown in Fig. 4A is identical to that of Fig. 3B and the possible way of assembly of Au-NPs is proposed to be liked as Scheme 2B. It means electrostatic attraction followed by hydrogen bonding interaction by the MCPACs leads to the formation of Au-NPs assembly. Being circular shape with highly positive charges, MCPACs at this pH, may act as cross-linkers for assembling Au-NPs. With the increase of pH from 6.50, where MCPAC is expected to have fully protonated, to 8.84 the net charge of the 28-MCPAC decreases from +6 to a lesser number as few of $-\text{NH}_2^+$ moieties de-protonate to become $-\text{NH}-$ present in the skeleton of 28-MCPAC. The recorded UV-Vis spectra with time show a distinctive change and are shown in Fig. 4B. There are rather sharp peak which shifts from *ca.* 540 nm (0 h) to 560 nm (12 h) along with a shoulder peak at *ca.* 605 nm appeared. The appearance of this type of spectrum may cause of increase of closeness of Au-particles with some sense of aggregation. This is may be due to the decrease of strong electrostatic force of attraction between the MCPACs and Au-NPs.

Again increase of pH to 11.50 (Fig. 4C) the shoulder peak at higher wavelength becomes quite sharp at *ca.* 605 nm and becomes broaden with time. At this pH it is expected that almost all $-\text{NH}_2^+$ groups converts into $-\text{NH}-$ groups. Thus, only hydrogen bond interaction ($-\text{COO}^- \cdots \text{H}-\text{N}-$) would be present between the citrate ions and 28-MCPAC. The change of spectral features with increasing pH indicates the assembly of Au-NPs into anisotropic chain arrays which is somewhat different in nature where cross-linking properties of MCPACs are ruled out. Further increase of pH to 12.30 and taking UV-Vis spectra (Fig. 4D) reveals no remarkable changes but the spectrum becomes stable with absorption maxima at *ca.* 540 nm (lesser intensive) and 630 nm (more intensive). At this pH it is expected that the group of $-\text{NH}_2^+$ (ammonium) of 28-MCPAC changes to mostly the group of $-\text{NH}-$ (amine) and a few of $-\text{N}^+$ (amide) due to de-protonation at higher pH. The formation of hydrogen

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra of Au-NPs with 28-MCPAC at various pH of molar ratio Au-NPs : 28-MCPAC is 2 : 3. Solutions pH (A) pH 6.50, (B) pH 8.84, (C) pH 11.50, (D) pH 12.30; period after spectra recorded : (a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 2 h, (d) 3 h, (e) 12 h, (f) 13 h, (g) 14 h, (h) 15, (i) 16 h.

bonding interaction ($-\text{COO}^- \cdots \text{H-N}-$) between 28-MCPAC and citrate ions may be the only guiding force for making assembly. The TEM image (discussed in TEM characterization) of Au-NPs at pH 12.30 reveal the consistent result with the UV-Vis spectra. Somewhat different way Beverina²⁶ tuned the assembly of NPs by tuning the number of branched pyridine moieties in its cross-linkers. Orbatch *et al.*¹⁴ controlled the assembling of citrated stabilized Au-NPs by tuning the electron density over the cross-linker moieties. Moreover, from the study of effect

of pH it is quite clear that the formation Au-NPs assembly is predominately occur at pH 6.5 where both electrostatic attraction and hydrogen bonding interaction are assumed to be happened and MCPAC may act as cross-linkers.

TEM characterization :

The TEM images of citrated stabilized Au-NPs in the presence of 32-MCPAC (Fig. 5A) and 28-MCPAC (Fig. 5B) at pH 6.5 are shown in Fig. 5. The TEM image of Au-NPs in the presence of 28-MCPAC at pH 12.5 is also

Fig. 5. TEM images of Au-NPs mixed with (A) 32-MCPAC, molar ratio 1 : 1, (B) 28-MCPAC, molar ratio, 1 : 1, (C) 28-MCPAC at pH 12.30.

taken and is shown in Fig. 5C. The TEM of citrate-stabilized gold nanoparticles (Fig. 1A) reveals that the particles are discrete with average diameter ~ 12 nm. Moreover, from the TEM images of Au-NPs in the presence MCPAC it is evident that in the presence of 32-MCPAC (Fig. 5A) and 28-MCPAC (Fig. 5B) the particles come at the vicinity and assemble into a pseudo 2-D network. Here it is worth mentioning that the electrostatic force of attraction followed by hydrogen bonding interaction between 32-/28-MCPAC and the citrate ions at pH 6.5 lowers the ζ potential of the Au-NPs. As a result Au-NPs come at the close vicinity and make pseudo 2-D array. Formation of pseudo 2-D array may be due to the fact that MCPACs carrying multiple positive charges act as cross-linkers. In comparison with the reported cross-linkers¹⁹, it is evident that MCPACs makes somewhat mono-layered pseudo 2-D assembly of Au-NPs. 32-MCPAC aided assembly with some sort of aggregation as shown in the TEM-image (Fig. 5A) may be due to the high charge of it that makes the process rather faster. Moreover, all results are coincident with UV-Vis spectra. Another striking feature is that when the positive charges on the MCPAC were reducing by increasing the basicity of its solution and added into the solution of Au-NPs, the particles were also prone to aggregate. The TEM of a solution of Au-NPs in the presence 28-MCPAC at pH 12.30 is shown in Fig. 5C. The TEM image reveals that the particles are aggregated in larger, dense rod-like 1-D aggregation. The nature of this type of aggregation may be due to the interactions of negatively charged citrate ions with neutral macrocyclic polyamine moiety through hydrogen bonding ($-\text{COO}^- \cdots \text{H-N}-$).

Photograph of the solutions :

The photograph of all the solutions is shown in Fig. 6. All the solutions are labeled as : citrate stabilized Au-

NPs (Fig. 6A), Au-NPs in the presence of 32-MCPAC with different molar ratios in the parentheses (Fig. 6B (1 : 3), 6C (2 : 3) and 6D (1 : 1)) and Au-NPs in presence of 28-MCPAC with different molar ratios (Fig. 6E (1 : 3), 6F (2 : 3) and 6G (1 : 1)). The color of the citrate-stabilized Au-NPs is red-wine (Fig. 6A). However, in the presence of 32-/28-MCPAC the color changes from red-wine (Fig. 6A) to blue (Fig. 6D or 6G), indicating the assembling of Au-NPs. To make assembly Au-NPs the molar ratio of Au-NPs to MCPAC has pronounced effect. From the photograph it is evident visibly. For instances, molar ratio 1 : 1 (bluish in color) (Au-NPs to 32-/28-MCPAC) leads to assemble of Au-NPs more effectively than that of other molar ratios, say 1 : 3 and 1 : 2 (reddish-blue in colour).

Fig. 6. Photographs of solutions (A) Au-NPs without MCPAC; (B)-(D) Au-NPs : 32-MCPAC, 1 : 3 (B), 2 : 3 (C) and 1 : 1 (D); (E)-(G) Au-NPs : 28-MCPAC, 1 : 3 (E), 2 : 3 (F), and 1 : 1 (G).

Conclusions

In this report, we employed macrocyclic polyammonium cations, 32-/28-MCPAC as cross-linkers to organize citrate-stabilized Au-NPs into an array. The results furnish the potential of these MCPACs for the fabrication of 2-D array of Au-NPs in water and were monitored by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. By the formation of assembly, the solution absorption spectra became broaden with a band centered at *ca.* 580 nm for 32-MCPAC and at *ca.* 605 nm for 28-MCPAC which are attributed inter-particle plasmon coupling. The concrete and visible proofs were obtained from the TEM images that revealed that Au-NPs were made mono-layered pseudo 2-D assembly. An additional visible proof earned from the photographs.

A distinctive color change was observed between discrete Au-NPs (wine-red) and assembled Au-NPs (bluish-red to blue). The pH effect on assemble of Au-NPs was also studied. It was seen that the preferable pH for the formation of Au-NPs assembly in a 2-D array is 6.50. At high pH 12.50 particles were aggregated in different way to make dense rod-like 1-D aggregation. We demonstrated that the electrostatic attraction followed by hydrogen bonding interaction between MCPACs and citrate ions led to the organization of Au-NPs into 2-D array in water at pH 6.50. It is very convenient and easy ways to have monolayered 2-D assembly of Au-NPs which would be futuristic promising materials, especially for optoelectronic devices. 32-/28-MCPAC, which has a brand name of anion recognizer, could be used as a cross-linker for assembling metal nanoparticles.

Experimental

Materials :

Hydrogen tetrachloroaurate(III) tetrahydrate (BDH, England), trisodiumcitrate (Wako, Osaka), were purchased from the companies indicated in the parentheses. All chemicals were analytical reagent grade and were used as received without any further purification. Purified water (18 M Ω cm) from a Milli-Q water purification system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) was used to prepare all solutions. Macrocyclic polyammonum cations, 28- and 32-MCPAC were prepared following the reported methods^{28,30}.

Preparation of aqueous Au-NPs by citrate reduction method :

Au-NPs (particle diameter ~12 nm) were prepared by following the citrate reduction method³⁴. To a 50 ml aqueous solution of HAuCl₄ (1 mM) under boiling condition was added 2 ml trisodium citrate dihydrate (0.2 M). The solution initially developed a grey color, which finally changed to a red within a few minutes with continuous boiling. It was stored and used for further experiments. The pH of the Au-NPs is 6.5. The average particle size is ~12 nm.

Preparation of citrate-stabilized Au-NPs-32-/28-MCPAC solutions :

To prepare assembly of Au-NPs the different molar ratios of Au-NPs to 32-/28-MCPAC as 1 : 3 (A), 1 : 2

(B), 2 : 3 (C) and 1 : 1 (D) and so on were executed. Initially the concentrations of 32-/28-MCPAC were kept higher and were reducing successively. It was observed that the color of the Au-NPs solutions had changed slowly for the solutions having higher concentration of 32-/28-MCPAC but it had changed rapidly for the solution having lower concentration of 32-/28-MCPAC. From the UV-Vis study the optimum molar ratio of Au-NPs to 32-MCPAC i.e. 6 : 1 for the onset of assembly formation was determined.

Preparation of pH solutions of Au-NPs-28-MCPAC :

pH of the aqueous solution of as-prepared 28-MCPAC is 4.55. Various solutions of pH 6.50, 8.84, 11.50 and 12.30 of 28-MCPAC were prepared by adding 0.1(N) NaOH solution. Au-NPs-28-MCPAC solutions at the above pH were prepared maintaining the molar ratio Au-NPs to 28-MCPAC of 2 : 3. UV-Vis spectra of all the solutions were recorded maintaining specified time interval.

Characterization :

UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded on a Hitachi U-3200 spectrophotometer using quartz cell with a path length of 1 cm. pH of all the solutions were measured using a PHM210 standard pH meter (Radiometer, Copenhagen). Samples for Transmission Electronic Microscopy (TEM) were prepared by placing a drop of the aqueous solution of Au-NPs onto a copper micro-grid and drying at room temperature. TEM micrographs were taken on Hitachi H-7100 TEM at acceleration voltage 75 kV.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indeed thankful to Professor C. Y. Liu, Professor in Chemistry, National Taiwan University, Taipei, Taiwan for helping in taking TEM images of Au-NPs. The authors are also thankful to National Institute of Technology, Agartala, Tripura, India for carrying out all other works.

References

1. X. Huang, P. K. Jain, I. H. El-Sayed and M. A. El-Sayed, *Nanomedicine*, 2007, **2**, 681.
2. M. C. Daniel and D. Astruc, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 293.
3. I. Biondi, G. Laurency and P. J. Dyson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **50**, 8038.
4. Y. Wang, X. L. Ma, Y. Wen, Y. Q. Zheng, G. P. Duan, Z.

- R. Zhang and H. F. Yang, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2010, **157**, K5.
5. A. Albanese and W. C. W. Chan, *ACS Nano*, 2011, **5**, 5478.
 6. Y. Zhou, Z. Yang and M. Xu, *Anal. Methods*, 2012, **4**, 2711.
 7. A. R. Tao, D. P. Ceperley, P. Sinsermsuksakul, A. R. Neureuther and P. D. Yang, *Nano Lett.*, 2008, **8**, 4033.
 8. D. Kisailus, M. Najarian, J. C. Weaver and D. E. Morse, *Adv. Matter.*, 2005, **17**, 1234.
 9. J. Liao, L. Bernard, M. Langer, C. Schönenberger and M. Calame, *Adv. Matter.*, 2006, **18**, 2444.
 10. K. Kim, H. B. Lee, J. W. Lee, H. K. Park and K. S. Shin, *Langmuir*, 2008, **24**, 7178.
 11. Y. Lu, G. L. Liu and L. P. Lee, *Nano Lett.*, 2005, **5**, 5.
 12. P. Mulvaney, *Langmuir*, 1996, **12**, 788.
 13. S.-K. Eah, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2011, **2**, 16866.
 14. M. Orbach, M. Lahav, P. Milko, S. G. Wolf and M. E. van der Boom, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2012, **51**, 7142.
 15. A. Das, S. Das and A. K. Raychaudhuri, *Bull. Mater. Sci.*, 2008, **31**, 277.
 16. Y.-K. Park, S.-H. Yoo and S. Park, *Langmuir*, 2008, **24**, 4370.
 17. J. Huang, A. R. Tao, S. Conner, R. He and P. Yang, *Nano Lett.*, 2006, **6**, 524.
 18. K.-S. Cho, D. V. Talapin, W. Gaschler and C. B. Murray, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 7140.
 19. A. N. Shipway, M. Lahav, R. Gabai and I. Willner, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 8789.
 20. A. Mocanu, I. Cernicab, G. Tomoaiac, L.-D. Bobosa, O. Horovitz and M. Tomoiaia-Cotisel, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 2009, **338**, 93.
 21. L. Wang, G. Wei, C. Guo, L. Sun, Y. Sun, Y. Song, T. Yang and Z. Li, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 2008, **312**, 148.
 22. E. Filippoa, A. Serraa, A. Buccolierib and D. Mannob, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 2013, **417**, 10.
 23. S. A. Maier, P. G. Kik, H. A. Atwater, S. Meltzer, E. Harel, B. E. Koel and A. A. G. Requicha, *Nat. Mater.*, 2003, **2**, 229.
 24. M. Sastry, K. S. Mayya and K. Bandyopadhyay, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 1997, **127**, 221.
 25. K. S. Mayya, V. Patil and M. Sastry, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 3944.
 26. L. Beverina, *ChemPhysChem.*, 2010, **11**, 2075.
 27. E. Garcia-España, P. Diaz, J. M. Llinares and A. Bianchi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 2952.
 28. C. Y. Liu and W. H. Chen, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1998, **815**, 251.
 29. C. Y. Liu, T. H. Chen and T. K. Misra, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2007, **1154**, 407.
 30. T. K. Misra, T. S. Chen, K. T. Wong and C. Y. Liu, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **52**, 793.
 31. T. K. Misra, K. P. Hung and C. Y. Liu, *J. Colloid. Interface Sci.*, 2010, **344**, 137.
 32. T. K. Misra and C. Y. Liu, *J. Nanopart. Res.*, 2009, **11**, 1053.
 33. T. K. Misra and C. Y. Liu, *J. Colloid. Interface Sci.*, 2008, **326**, 411.
 34. T. K. Misra, T. S. Chen and C. Y. Liu, *J. Colloid. Interface Sci.*, 2006, **297**, 584.
 35. J. A. Creighton and D. G. Eadon, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, **87**, 3881.
 36. M. Kerker, "The Scattering of Light and Other Electromagnetic Radiation", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 38.
 37. S. Lin, M. Li, E. Dujardin, C. Girard and S. Mann, *Adv. Mater.*, 2005, **17**, 2553.
 38. K. H. Su, Q. H. Wei, X. Zhang, J. J. Mock, D. R. Smith and S. Schultz, *Nano Lett.*, 2003, **3**, 1087.
 39. Y.-Z. Xu, Y.-R. Zhang, J.-F. Zheng, C. Guo, Z.-J. Niu and Z.-L. Li, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2011, **6**, 664.